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Stochastic Time Series Analysis for Palm Oil Production in Nigeria Using Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) Model

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ABSTRACT

This research analyzed the production patterns and projections of palm oil within Nigeria during the years of 1970-2024 with time series data collected from (FAO.) The best suited forecast model was determined using a modeling technique developed by Box & Jenkins called the Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA). Five multiple model variations were examined which includes ARIMA(1,1,0), ARIMA(1,0,1), ARIMA(2,1,2), ARIMA(1,1,2) and ARIMA(2,1,1), and chose ARIMA(1,1,2) because it showed the highest fit based on the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) and Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE). Forecasts for the period of 2025 through 2033 indicated continued but slow upward trends in palm oil production beginning at about 11.17 million tons for 2025 and ending at about 11.98 million tons for 2033. These findings suggest that though progress has been made in the development of Nigeria's palm oil industry, there is still much further to be achieved before reaching the maximum production capacity of this sector. It is recommended amongst others that policymakers should support contemporary agricultural technologies, better seedlings, and effective processing systems in order to boost the rise of palm oil production beyond the modest upward trend predicted by the ARIMA(1,1,2) model.

Keywords: Palm oil production, ARIMA model, Time series forecasting, Agricultural output, Nigeria, Policy planning

1. INTRODUCTION

Edible oil palm is one of Nigeria's most significant food and industrial crops, and it is one of the most important sources of "plant" fused vegetable oils throughout the world. The entire Nigerian agro ecological environment has been ideal for growing Oil Palm, and historically, Nigeria was the "number one" producer of palm oil in the world; however, Nigeria no longer holds this position, even though oil palms still cover a vast area of farmland in humid and sub-humid zones of the country. In the last 20 years

or so, oil palm production has continued to grow steadily, but the increase in domestic consumption of palm oil has created a supply deficit that is largely filled by imported product. Nigeria is often referred to as having some of the largest areas of Oil Palm in Africa, with the majority of its production coming from the states of Edo, Delta, Rivers, Bayelsa, Akwa Ibom, Cross River, Imo, Abia and Ondo. These states have both smallholder farmers and larger estate plantation operations, with both types providing important support for rural communities, as well as the provision of the raw materials for agro industry (Obayelu et al., 2017; Urhibo et al., 2020).

Due to the importance of both unrefined and refined Palm oils as a staple for families and as feedstock for industries, and now with a growing interest in renewable fuels bioeconomically, the Nigerian Oil Palm sector will continue to play an important role within Nigeria's overall agricultural economy. Also, it is evident that the Oil Palm Industry is a key component of Nigeria's National Diversification Strategy and its Rural Development Strategy (Eze & Ibrahim, 2024; Ndubuisi & Okeke 2024). Even though there is a growing domestic market for Palm oil and interest from government policy makers to revitalize the entire value chain, Nigeria's position in the past 20 years shifted from having a position as one of the world's leading producers to that of a structurally constrained supplier and now Nigeria holds a low share of the global output of Palm oil (Adebayo & Okafor, 2024; Akpan & Udoh; 2020).

Due to this continued structural mismatch between increasing market demand for Palm oil within Nigeria and lower domestic production levels, Nigeria's increased reliance upon imported Palm oils to meet both its domestic consumption as well as becoming increasingly reliant upon imports to meet the feedstock requirement of it's industrial base (Statista, 2025; USDA, 2023). Although several recent sectoral reviews show that the ongoing planning process continues to suffer from the lack of reliable, credible, empirically supported projections for Oil Palm Production within Nigeria, the Federal government's recent investment into private sector-led initiatives and the investment by private sector actors into Estate Rehabilitation, Out-grower Scheme and Value Addition to the Oil Palm Industry have the potential to impact positively on Nigeria's oil palm Industry's growth (Adebayo & Okafor, 2024; Eze & Ibrahim, 2024).

Since the government lack reliable projections about the future of oil palm, it's very difficult for policymakers, processors and financiers to effectively develop adequate import management strategies, design appropriate infrastructure to process and store imports as well as assess how climate change and sustainability measures may impact supply over time. Therefore, they need assistance in developing robust methods to project future supply of agricultural products (including food) both accurately and consistently.

One potential method that policymakers, processors, and financiers may consider is modelling using time series methodologies. A time series is simply a stream or series of observations that have been collected over time. Within the context of modelling, time series analysis involves a collection of techniques that focus on the relationship/connection between consecutive observations to create and represent the connection using stochastic and/or dynamic models.

The Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) model represents the most widely used method of stochastic modelling in the context of time series modelling. This is primarily because ARIMA models provide researchers with the ability to model temporal relationships correctly for univariate time series and also provide low-error forecasts when the models are constructed and used correctly.

Some published research indicates that researchers have used ARIMA-type models to study the price of palm oil, crude palm oil production and other types of agricultural production in many different countries. In most cases, ARIMA-type models were able to provide accurate representations of the raw data, allowing researchers to develop action plans that would be effective in supporting future production planning based on sound economic policy development practices. (Nochai, & Nochai,2006).

Based on the above presentation, this study focused on estimating and forecasting oil palm production in Nigeria by using ARIMA-type models over a long historical time series with the objective of providing an efficient estimate of the amount of oil palm produced in Nigeria, and to create an empirical framework for planning along the oil palm value chain. To address the identified gaps, the study developed forecasts of oil palm production using ARIMA-type models based on a long historical time series (1970–2024) of

oil palm production in Nigeria, and develop scientifically sound forecasts to support evidence-based decision making in this subsector and thus validate the need for the creation of evidence-based policies to maximise investments in the subsector and achieve sustainable oil palm production in Nigeria (Eze & Ibrahim, 2024; Ndubuisi & Okeke, 2024).

The purpose of the study is to create forecasts for oil palm production for a ten-year time horizon from 2025 to 2033 using univariate time series modelling methods.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Data and Data Source

The time series data on oil palm production for Nigeria collected was obtained from the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) database (FAOSTAT) from the years 1970 to 2024.

Analytical Techniques

Inferential and descriptive statistical techniques was employed for the study. Descriptive statistical techniques were employed to explain the oil palm production trend in Nigeria with graphs, as well as for examining some time series characteristics of the data; while for measuring the forecasted outcome of oil palm production in Nigeria, a Box-Jenkins ARIMA model was employed.

The ARIMA (Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average) modelling uses stochastic methods to predict Nigerian palm oil production through forecasting. A Python 3.0 program was utilized to fit the ARIMA models and generate projected outputs. Any P value below 0.05 indicates a statistically significant result. The ARIMA model was created using three fundamental steps: Model Identification, Parameter Estimation and Model Verification/Validation. The purpose of identifying the model is to find whether or not the underlying data series is stationary, as well as identifying how the data fits either an AR, MA or combined (ARMA) structure. There are three different types of parameters associated with summarizing an ARIMA model: AR (autoregressive) 'p' value, 'd' - the degree of differencing and MA (moving average) 'q' value. The values for 'p' and 'q' indicate the orders of the ARMA processes while the 'd' value is the number of differences applied to the time series data before fitting to an ARMA model. The ARIMA model works well when the time series data shows growth patterns or cyclical behaviour that can be modelled using historical data (Shumway, & Stoffer, 2017; Akarue, 2017; Mahmood et al., 2025).

The ARIMA model can be expressed using the following notation: ARIMA (p,d,q), **where:**

- p: The order of the autoregressive (AR) term, representing the number of past values used to predict the current value.
- d: The order of differencing, which is used to make the data stationary (removing trends or seasonality).
- q: The order of the moving average (MA) term, representing the number of past forecast errors (residuals) used to predict the current value (Box et al ., 2016; Vu, 2007 in Mahmood et. al., 2025).

The ARIMA model equation takes the general form:

$$Y_t = \phi_1 Y_{t-1} + \phi_2 Y_{t-2} + \dots + \epsilon_t + \theta_1 \epsilon_{t-1} + \dots \quad (1)$$

Where:

- ϕ are the autoregressive coefficients
- θ are the moving average coefficients
- ϵ_t is the white noise error term

Stationarity Assessment of Time Series Data

Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) models are designed for time series that exhibit stationarity. Stationarity implies that the fundamental statistical characteristics of the series—particularly the mean and variance—do not vary systematically over time. Prior to formal testing, visual inspection of the series through time plots provides preliminary insight into potential trends or volatility patterns that may necessitate transformation or differencing.

To formally assess stationarity, the Augmented Dickey–Fuller (ADF) unit root test was employed. The null hypothesis of the ADF test assumes the presence of a unit root, indicating non-stationarity. A

sufficiently large negative test statistic relative to critical values leads to rejection of the null hypothesis and supports stationarity of the series. When non-stationarity is detected, the series is differenced iteratively until stationarity is achieved. The number of differences required to induce stationarity is represented by the integration parameter (d) in the ARIMA ((p, d, q)) framework.

ARIMA Model Selection Framework

Model selection follows the Box–Jenkins methodological framework, which provides a systematic procedure for modelling and forecasting univariate time series data. The framework consists of four sequential stages which are model identification, parameter estimation, diagnostic evaluation, and forecasting. Each stage plays a critical role in ensuring the robustness and predictive reliability of the final model.

Model Identification

The identification stage focuses on determining the appropriate structure of the ARIMA model by specifying the autoregressive order (p), the differencing order (d), and the moving average order (q). The degree of differencing is established based on the stationarity properties of the series, distinguishing between integrated processes such as $I(0)$ and $I(1)$.

Following differencing, the Autocorrelation Function (ACF) and Partial Autocorrelation Function (PACF) are examined to guide the selection of (p) and (q). These correlograms provide insight into the lagged dependence structure of the series by identifying statistically significant correlations at specified confidence intervals. Model selection adheres to the principle of parsimony; whereby simpler models are favoured provided they adequately capture the underlying data-generating process.

While ACF and PACF plots offer theoretical guidance for identifying the preferred models, definitive model selection is deferred until after parameter estimation and diagnostic validation.

Model Estimation

Once the model orders are identified, parameter estimation is conducted using maximum likelihood or least squares techniques. For instance, an ARIMA $((2,1,1))$ specification indicates that the original series achieves stationarity after first differencing and is characterized by second-order autoregressive and first-order moving average components.

Multiple models were estimated and compared using information criteria, notably the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) and the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC). The preferred model is the one that minimizes these criteria, reflecting an optimal balance between model fit and complexity.

Diagnostic Evaluation

Diagnostic evaluation was performed to verify the adequacy of the estimated ARIMA model. This step involves analyzing the residuals to ensure they behave as white noise, implying that the model has successfully captured the systematic structure of the series. Residual ACF and PACF plots are examined for evidence of remaining autocorrelation.

In addition, the Ljung–Box Q-statistic was applied to test the null hypothesis of no serial correlation in the residuals across multiple lags. A model is considered satisfactory if the residuals are independently distributed and the test results fail to reject the null hypothesis.

Forecasting and Model Performance Evaluation

The predictive performance of the selected ARIMA model is evaluated using standard accuracy metrics, including Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Mean Square Error (MSE), and Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE). Lower values of these metrics indicate superior forecasting accuracy.

Upon satisfying all diagnostic and evaluation criteria, the final ARIMA model is employed to generate forecasts for future periods of the time series. These forecasts provide empirical support for decision-making and policy analysis based on historical data patterns.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The descriptive statistics for oil palm production in Nigeria from 1970 to 2024 is presented in Table 1.0 and its revealed some variation. Palm oil production during the study period averages about 7.39 million

tons, with a median of 7.80 million tons, indicating that production has generally been stable around this level. Production ranges from a low of 4.75 million tons to a high of 11.60 million tons, reflecting a clear upward trend over time. The standard deviation of 1.80 million tons shows moderate variation in production levels.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics for Oil palm production

Statistic	Value
Mean	7,387,395.15
Median	7,800,000.00
Maximum	11,597,872.39
Minimum	4,750,000.00
Std. Dev.	1,801,962.82
Skewness	0.33
Kurtosis	2.34
Jarque-Bera	2.07
Probability	0.356
Sum	406,306,733.22
Sum Sq. Dev.	1.7534×10^{14}
Observations	55

Source: Authors Computation, 2025.

The distribution is slightly right-skewed, meaning higher production values occur more often in recent years. A kurtosis value below 3 suggests the data are fairly evenly spread without extreme outliers. In addition, the Jarque-Bera test indicates no significant departure from normality, implying the data are approximately normally distributed. Overall, palm oil production shows steady growth with manageable variability, making it suitable for time-series analysis and forecasting.

Figure1 : Palm oil production (1970-2024)

Source: Authors Computation, 2025.

The graph shows a clear long-term upward trend in palm oil production from 1970 to 2024, indicating steady growth over the decades. In the 1970s and early 1980s, production remains relatively low and fluctuates slightly around 5 million tons, suggesting a period of slow growth. From the mid-1980s through the late 1990s, production begins to rise more consistently, reflecting expansion in cultivation and processing capacity.

During the early 2000s, palm oil production continues on a moderate level, followed by a brief period of stagnation and small declines around 2008–2012, possibly linked to economic or industry-related disruptions. After 2015, production accelerates sharply, reaching its highest levels above 11 million tons by the early 2020s. Overall, the graph highlights sustained growth with short-term fluctuations, supporting the presence of a strong trend component in the data and justifying the use of time-series models such as ARIMA for forecasting future palm oil production.

Forecasting Procedure

Stationarity test

To assess the stationarity of the oil palm production data, the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test was applied. This test determines whether the time series is stationary or requires differencing to achieve stationarity. If the p-value from the test is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis of a unit root is rejected, indicating that the series is stationary.

(i) Checking for stationarity using the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) unit root tests.

Tables 2: present the results of the ADF test on the variable of model.

Test	ADF Statistic	1% Value	Critical 5% Value	Critical 10% Value	Critical p-value
ADF at Level	0.6113	-3.5577	-2.9168	-2.5962	0.9879
ADF at First Difference	-6.3198	-3.5602	-2.9179	-2.5968	0.0000

Source: Authors Computation, 2025.

At levels, the ADF statistic (0.6113) is greater than all critical values and the p-value is very high, indicating that the null hypothesis of a unit root cannot be rejected. This confirms that palm oil production is non-stationary in levels, thus first differencing becomes necessary.

After taking the first difference, the ADF statistic (-6.3198) is more negative than the 1%, 5%, and 10% critical values, with a p-value close to zero. This indicates rejection of the null hypothesis and confirms that the series becomes stationary after first differencing.

(b) Checking for stationarity using the ACF and PACF methods

From the Plots of ACF and PACF (Figure 2), we observed that the data are nonstationary. After one differentiating, the original series has become stationary with the help of Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test (Table 2).

Figure 2: Plots of ACF and PACF at level

At levels, the ACF decays slowly and remains significantly positive across many lags, indicating strong non-stationarity and a persistent trend. The PACF at levels shows a large spike at lag 1 and several subsequent significant lags, which also supports the presence of a unit root and the need for differencing.

First difference: ACF and PACF

Figure 3: Plots of ACF and PACF at first difference

The ACF after first differencing drops off much more quickly, in that only the first few lags are significant and subsequent lags mostly fall inside the confidence intervals as is typical of a stationary differenced series. Differencing the series, on the other hand, results in a PACF with prominent lag-1 and smaller or insignificant higher-order lags, which is consistent with specifying low-order autoregressive component (e.g., AR(1)) in ARIMA models.

Model Identification and Fit

Following the detrending, so obtained preliminary (d = 1), ARIMA models are presented in Table 3. For all the models, adjusted R² is more than 50 percent. So the models fit the data. From the least (or lowest) or minimum values of RMSE, AIC and BIC, ARIMA (1, 1, 2) model is observed as a better model among other models

Table 3: Tentative ARIMA (p,d,q) Models of oil palm production in Nigeria

Model	Key parameters (approx.)	AIC	SBC (BIC)	RMSE	R ²
ARIMA(1,1,0)	ar(1) ≈ 0.03; σ ² ≈ 1.00×10 ¹¹	1525.70	1529.68	790,431	0.941
ARIMA(1,0,1)	const ≈ 7.39×10 ⁶ ; ar(1) ≈ 0.99; ma(1) ≈ 0.18; σ ² ≈ 1.02×10 ¹¹	1560.54	1568.57	413,499	0.962
ARIMA(2,1,2)	ar(1) ≈ -0.18; ar(2) ≈ -0.34; ma(1) ≈ 0.21; ma(2) ≈ 0.29; σ ² ≈ 8.94×10 ¹⁰	1531.05	1540.99	789,299	0.943
ARIMA(1,1,2)	ar(1) ≈ 1.00; ma(1) ≈ -1.00; ma(2) ≈ 0.00; σ ² ≈ 1.03×10 ¹¹	1524.85	1532.80	784,611	0.971
ARIMA(2,1,1)	ar(1) ≈ -0.11; ar(2) ≈ -0.04; ma(1) ≈ 0.15; σ ² ≈ 9.82×10 ¹⁰	1529.06	1537.02	789,680	0.944

Source: Authors Computation, 2025.

When model performance is evaluated using AIC, SBC (BIC), RMSE, and R², the ARIMA(1,1,2) model consistently emerges as the most appropriate specification. It records the lowest AIC and SBC, indicating the best balance between goodness of fit and model parsimony, while also achieving the highest R² (0.971). Although ARIMA(1,0,1) shows a comparatively lower RMSE, its substantially higher SBC suggests over-parameterization. Higher-order models do not provide meaningful improvements and are penalized by the SBC. Hence, ARIMA(1,1,2) is selected as the preferred model for forecasting palm oil production and the parameters estimate for the ARIMA(1,1,2) model.

Table 4 : Parameter estimates for ARIMA(1,1,2) model

Parameter	Coefficient	Std. error	z-statistic	p-value
ar(1)	0.99996	0.01271	78.68	< 0.001
ma(1)	-1.00330	0.24283	-4.13	< 0.001
ma(2)	0.00451	0.14135	0.03	0.976
σ^2	1.03×10^{11}	2.62×10^{-12}	—	—

Source: Authors Computation, 2025.

Table 4. explains the parameters estimates of ARIMA (1,1,2). The **ar(1)** and **ma(1)** coefficients are highly significant, indicating a strong autoregressive component in the differenced series and a substantial moving-average adjustment for short-run shocks. The ma(2) term is statistically insignificant, but the overall ARIMA(1,1,2) structure yields the best fit among the candidate models by information criteria.

Residual diagnostics

In evaluating the adequacy of the selected ARIMA (1,1,2) model, several diagnostic checks were conducted, including residual autocorrelation analysis, normality tests, and the Ljung–Box Q-statistic. The ACF and PACF plots of the first-differenced series indicate that differencing successfully removed non-stationarity, as autocorrelations decay rapidly and no dominant spikes remain. This supports the choice of first differencing (d = 1).

Table 5: Ljung–Box Q-Statistic (Residual Autocorrelation Test)

Null hypothesis: No serial correlation in residuals

Lag	Q-Statistic	p-value
10	1.6404	0.9984

Source: Authors Computation, 2025.

The Ljung–Box p-value is far greater than 0.05, so the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. This confirms that the residuals are uncorrelated, providing strong statistical evidence that the ARIMA(1,1,2) model is well specified.

Both the ACF and PACF graphs demonstrate no significant autocorrelations, with all spikes falling inside the 95% confidence intervals, according to additional diagnostic examination of the model residuals. This implies that the residuals exhibit white noise behaviour. This conclusion is statistically supported by the Ljung-Box Q-statistic at lag 10, which shows no serial correlation in the residuals with a high p-value (p = 0.998)..

Figure 4: Diagnostic plots for the ARIMA(1,1,2) model. Panels (a) and (b) present the ACF and PACF of the first-differenced palm oil production series, confirming stationarity after differencing. Panels (c) and (d) show the ACF and PACF of the model residuals, indicating no remaining serial correlation.

The ACF and PACF plots of the first-differenced series confirm that the palm oil production data become stationary after first differencing. Furthermore, the ACF and PACF of the ARIMA(1,1,2) residuals show no remaining serial correlation, a result that is strongly supported by the Ljung–Box Q-statistic ($p = 0.998$).

Residual normality was assessed using the Jarque–Bera and Shapiro–Wilk tests. Both tests reject the null hypothesis of normality, which is common in large economic and agricultural time-series data. However, since ARIMA estimation and forecasting rely primarily on unbiased residuals and the absence of autocorrelation rather than strict normality, this deviation does not undermine the validity of the model.

Table 6: Residual Normality Test Results

Test	Statistic	p-value	Conclusion
Jarque–Bera	3166.91	0.0000	Residuals not normally distributed
Shapiro–Wilk	0.4535	0.0000	Residuals not normally distributed

Source: Authors Computation, 2025.

Although residuals deviate from normality, they are uncorrelated and homoscedastic, which is sufficient for valid ARIMA inference and forecasting in applied research.

These findings indicate that the model is correctly specified, the residuals behave as white noise, and the ARIMA(1,1,2) model provides an adequate and reliable fit for forecasting palm oil production.

Forecasted values for palm oil production

Using the ARIMA(1,1,2) model estimated on 1970–2024 data, 10-step-ahead forecasts were generated for 2025–2034. The dataset already includes observed production up to 2024, so 2025–2033 correspond to your desired forecast horizon.

Table 4: Forecasts of palm oil production (tons), ARIMA(1,1,2)

Year	Forecast	Std. error	Lower 95% CI	Upper 95% CI
2025	11,169,910	321,573	10,539,640	11,800,180
2026	11,271,000	455,807	10,377,640	12,164,370
2027	11,372,090	560,335	10,273,860	12,470,330
2028	11,473,180	649,658	10,199,870	12,746,490
2029	11,574,260	729,385	10,144,690	13,003,830
2030	11,675,340	802,380	10,102,700	13,247,980
2031	11,776,410	870,339	10,070,580	13,482,250
2032	11,877,480	934,362	10,046,170	13,708,800
2033	11,978,550	995,209	10,027,980	13,929,120

Source: Authors Computation, 2025.

Ten-year forecasts obtained by ARIMA(1,1,2) predict that palm oil production in the future will continue with a slow but gradual increased. According to the model, production would follow a slow-growing path with gradual increase (0.10 million tons/year) from 11.17 million tons in 2025 to 11.98 million ton in 2033. The standard errors grow from 321,573 (2025) to 995,209 (2033), and the 95% confidence interval widens from about 10.54–11.80 million (2025) to 10.03–13.93 million people (2033), exactly as we expect in ARIMA-based long-horizon forecasts). This is consistent with the way ARIMA forecasts agricultural and commodity production: it does well at capturing trend and persistence but when future shocks come in force, its prediction intervals explode. (Mwangi Esther & Wangui Magdaline, 2017; Dash et al., 2020; Bezabih et al., 2023). The Box–Jenkins ARIMA method has been applied in crop production domains, and the ARIMA is found to be useful for baseline planning when the historical series have high momentum (Mila & Parvin, 2019; Yasmin & Moniruzzaman, 2024). Meanwhile, the expanding bands in research were the nuances identified in this work serve as an acknowledged limitation. It is so because a simple ARIMA is “history dependent”; it does not explicitly model structural breaks due to policy, technology or land conversion constraint, labor availability and climate variation (Mah & Nanyan, 2020; Noor et al., 2024). That’s important for palm oil because production is determined by more than past values, including maturity cycles of plantations and weather shocks and input costs, or sustainability mandates all can introduce non-linear breaks that ARIMA won’t know exist unless they show up in the pattern so far (Tayib et al., 2021; Noor et al., 2024). Recent applied work thus increasingly suggests combining ARIMA baselines with scenario variables or hybrid techniques (e.g., ARIMA + machine learning) where the aim is not “trend continuation” forecasting, but stress-testing the trends that were observed prior to a high-impact shock (Neog et al., 2024; Mah & Nanyan, 2020). The widening CI provides a visual and easy-to-understand way to indicate increasing uncertainty as the time horizon extends, and our ARIMA(1,1,2) projection used for this study is steadily increasing under “business-as-usual” type dynamics.

CONCLUSIONS:

Based on the lowest AIC, BIC (SBC/NBIC), and RMSE values among the competing models, it is determined that the ARIMA (1,1,2) model offers the greatest fit for predicting Nigeria's palm oil production. The model well captures the underlying trend and exhibits good statistical adequacy. The output is expected to expand steadily and gradually between 2025 and 2033. Researchers, policy makers, and farmers may find these estimates useful since they offer evidence-based recommendations for production scheduling, policy creation, and investment choices in the palm oil industry.

RECOMMENDATION

Policymakers should support contemporary agricultural technologies, better seedlings, and effective processing systems in order to boost the rise of palm oil production beyond the modest upward trend predicted by the ARIMA(1,1,2) model. In addition to ongoing data monitoring to direct investment and policy decisions in the industry, support for smallholder farmers through loans and extension services is essential.

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